

TYPES OF INTERTEXTUALITY AND ITS USAGE IN FORMAL SPEECH

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Annotation. Intertextuality, which is considered one of the lexical components of formal communication, was selected as the main research object of this article, and sufficient information is given in the article about the entry of the term into science, the usage areas and its types.

Key words. Intertextuality, text, meaning, field, formal speech.

Annotatsiya. Rasmiy muloqotning leksik tarkibiy qismlaridan biri hisoblangan intertekstuallik mazkur maqolaning asosiy tadqiqot obyekti sifatida tanlab olingan bo`lib, ushbu atamaning fanga kirib kelishi, ishlatilish sohalari va uning turlari haqida maqolada yetarlicha ma'lumot berilgan.

Kalit so`zlar. Intertekstuallik, tekst, ma'no, soha, rasmiy muloqot.

Аннотация. В качестве основного объекта исследования данной статьи выбрана интертекстуальность, которая считается одним из лексических компонентов формального общения, при этом в статье дается достаточная информация о вхождении термина в науку, сферах употребления и его видах.

Ключевые слова. Интертекстуальность, текст, смысл, поле, формальная речь.

Intertextuality is one of the units used as lexical tools expressing the subject's attitude to the dictum in formal speech. As the use of intertextuality in the process of communication increases the effectiveness and colourability of the speaker's speech, increases the impact and reliability of the message he wants to convey to the listener. What is intertextuality itself, let's first clarify it. There are several definitions to the word "intertextuality": the interrelationship between texts, especially works of literature; the way that similar or related texts influence, reflect, or differ from each other: the intertextuality between two novels with the same setting¹.

The term "intertextuality" describes how works of art, particularly literature, are related to and influence one another. Text, in this context, most often refers to a work of literature, like a book or poem, but it can be any creative work, such as a film, song, painting, or speech. Intertextuality often involves things like the similarities and differences between two pieces, but it

¹ <https://www.dictionary.com/browse/intertextuality#:~:text=noun,novels%20with%20the%20same%20setting>

can also cover a broad range of relationships between different works. Intertextuality is primarily used in literary and cultural criticism and analysis².

In Merriam Webster online dictionary the word is defined “the complex interrelationship between a text and other texts taken as basic to the creation or interpretation of the text”³

According to Oxford learners’ dictionary “the relationship between texts, especially literary texts”⁴.

One way to view it is through the definition of the word "intertextuality," which connects it to the labourers whose primary tool is language. Throughout these eras, authenticity plays a crucial role in effectively conveying the main idea.

Since the concept of intertextuality is evolving with the times, it can be regarded as one of humanity's most significant and cherished fields. In the era of the World Wide Web, references to trustworthy sources—which frequently take the form of historical accounts, classic works, films, essays, and so forth—are becoming more and more common. Modern psychology now resembles a mosaic, with many philosophies and ideas mixed together. In light of this, researchers' interest in examining the consistency of individuality in various types of discourse does not decrease.

The theory pertaining to the foundation of intertextuality defines individuality as the unique characteristic of some texts that exhibit indications of individual interaction. We examine the use of authenticity resources as a creative tool aimed at enhancing the efficacy of the marketing message by updating members of the linguistic community's knowledge and ideas in relation to historical cultural experiences, boosting the text's mnemonic power, and presenting socially significant information without stereotyping.

In accordance with the semiotic approach, text is viewed as a formalized system; hence, we examine visual arts like literature, paintings, sculptures, music, and architecture in addition to verbal phenomena.

The research on intertextuality demonstrates that authenticity not only conveys the primary message but also the message related to the related field under this information. Through the use of this method, the author not only expresses his opinion but also provides examples of other people's opinions regarding this information, increasing the opinion's efficacy, meaningfulness, and impact.

² <https://www.dictionary.com/browse/intertextuality#:~:text=noun,novels%20with%20the%20same%20setting>.

³ <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/intertextuality>

⁴ <https://www.oxfordlearnersdictionaries.com/definition/english/intertextuality?q=intertextuality>

We use intertextuality in many areas related to our social lives. As examples, we can cite public speaking, literature, marketing, politics, journalism, advertising services, and a host of other fields.

Intertextuality refers to the interdependence of texts in relation to one another (as well as to the culture at large). Texts can influence, derive from, parody, reference, quote, contrast with, build on, draw from, or even inspire each other. Intertextuality produces meaning. Knowledge does not exist in a vacuum, and neither does literature.⁵

In linguistics, "intertextuality" has many different meanings. The literary relationship between classic and contemporary works is discussed. Every writer starts out as a reader. Whether or not the other literary works are in the same genre as theirs, they nonetheless provide them with inspiration and ideas. If a writer draws inspiration from that piece of writing, he or she may mimic, employ prosody, cite, or quote that inspiration. Since "no literary work stands entirely alone," as scholar Julia Kristeva noted. In reality, every text is a "intertext," existing as a point of intersection between other literary works, in accordance with her thesis. Scholars divided intertextuality into 9 types:

1. *Allusion*- it is a subliminal allusion to another piece of art, usually made by bringing up a familiar detail about one of its themes, characters, or images.

2. *Quotation*- a direct quote is when a word from one text is used in another, usually surrounded by quote marks. It's also possible to use quotations as the titles of other works.

3. *Claque*- a linguistic phrase for loanwords that are directly translated is "calque." Although the term "calque" is more frequently used in linguistics than in literature, it is conceivable to employ it as a subtle sort of intertextuality.

4. *Homage*- an homage is a clear celebration and in-depth allusion to another author, figurehead, or body of work. Homages are intentional and incredibly expressive types of intertextuality that are typically hard to miss.

5. *Plagiarism*- the act of a writer stealing another person's words and trying to pass it off as their own is called plagiarism. Even yet, technically speaking, intertextuality includes plagiarism. It is strongly discouraged and regarded as creative and intellectual dishonesty.

6. *Translation*- The process of translating a work from one language to another involves more than simply technical skills; it also involves creativity and is inherently intertextual, resulting in a linguistic and cultural interaction between the two versions of the work.

⁵ <https://www.thoughtco.com/what-is-intertextuality-1691077>

7. *Pastiche*- a pastiche is an intentional stylistic appropriation of another piece of art or genre. A pastiche is when a writer writes in the 21st century while purposefully copying literary voices from the 19th century.

8. *Parody*- The word "parody" refers to light-hearted intertextual methods. To make a point, parodies frequently exaggerate and mock certain aspects of a work.

9. *Reimagining*- some forms of intertextuality create sweeping reimagining of existing works. Rewriting an existing work from the perspective of a different character, for instance, would fall into this category.⁶

Every form of intertextuality serves a distinct purpose and varies depending on its responsibility. Some of them assist writers in adapting or rewriting the old version to a new one, while others assist in imitation and practice. Illustration and quotation attempt to provide direct and indirect references to the work of other writers.

In summary, the purpose of incorporating intertextuality into public speaking, literature, and other forms of expression is to enhance the content of our speeches, clarify the meaning, create visually stunning scenes, and raise the work's sensitivity and colourability.

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